

Next-Generation Wind-farm Support Vessels: Evaluating the Impact of a Novel Hull and Thruster Layout

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Abstract. CSOVs (Construction/Service Operation Vessels) are multi-role vessels which are key to servicing offshore wind farms, operating at wind farm locations for extended periods of time. With increasing global demand for offshore wind farms and their cost-effectiveness, the performance requirements for these vessels are ever more demanding – higher operability, efficiency & maneuverability – where traditionally designed vessels become limited. Hence, a radical new concept was devised with a double-acting hull fitted with four identical azimuth thrusters at each corner of the vessel (Damen DPX-DRIVE™). The concept was tested and studied rigorously by both DAMEN and MARIN. This paper studies the impact of such a design choice on the performance of the vessel. Comparison with traditional ship designs is made for key performance aspects such as Dynamic Positioning (DP), Seakeeping and Resistance & Propulsion (R&P). Both static and dynamic DP assessments were performed numerically, showing an improved positioning capability and power efficiency for the new concept. Seakeeping model tests and numerical studies using MARIN's in-house software showed that the vessel motions are within NORDFORSK criteria for crew comfort and gangway operations for typical operational environments. However, with the raised bow shape, slamming impacts are expected in moderate to high seas. Model-scale R&P tests were performed in MARIN's towing tank, which showed a decrease in calm-water resistance for the new concept. However, the propulsion efficiency was found to be slightly lower, indicating the additional drag from the forward thrusters. Overall, the paper demonstrates that the design enables increased DP performance, improved onboard comfort and operability, all while reducing system complexity, maintenance, OPEX and CAPEX, without (significantly) compromising the seakeeping and propulsion performance.

Keywords: *Wind-farm support vessels, Ship Design, Dynamic positioning, Operability, Propulsive efficiency, Crew Comfort, Double-acting hull, Model-scale testing, Numerical simulations, Maneuverability, Noise, and vibration reduction*

1 Introduction

With most countries adopting global targets for energy transition and decarbonization, the demand for increasing share of renewable energy in the total energy mix is growing. Wind energy, particularly offshore wind energy forms a crucial part of this mix, and therefore the planning and mobilization of new offshore wind farms is rapidly accelerating. More and more offshore windfarms, both bottom-fixed and floating, are either already in operation or are planned to be in operation in the coming years and decades around the world.

For the construction and servicing of the windfarms, different types of vessels are required for different stages and purposes, the most notable ones being – Wind-turbine installation vessels (WTIV), construction/service operations vessels (C/SOVs) and crew transfer vessels (CTVs). Of the three, this paper focuses on the CSOV type vessels.

In the past decade, the construction and servicing of the offshore windfarms were undertaken by retrofit 'Walk-To-Work (W2W)' vessels which were Platform Supply Vessels (PSVs), or other offshore support vessels (OSVs) retrofitted with among other things, personnel access systems. Examples of such retrofits include the Norside fleet (Norside Cygnus, Norside Cetus), and Wagenborg fleet (Koeningsborg, Keizersborg, and Kroonborg) which were converted from PSV to W2W vessels by adding an accommodation block and walk-to-work gangway, among other things. However, with the limitations of such retrofits and increasing number of windfarms, there is now a growing demand for more dedicated Construction and/or Service Operation Vessels (C/SOVs) as they need to not only cater to the large number of wind turbines in more severe conditions, but also perform the operations as quickly and efficiently as possible, while keeping specialized personnel safe and comfortable during extended stays offshore. This growth demand is illustrated in Figure 1 below.

Such a specialized operation requires a vessel concept that offers high maneuverability, high operability and high comfort while staying at sea for weeks at a time. Given the demands and challenges of such operations, a conventional vessel design solution is not sufficient anymore. Hence, a new solution with four fixed and identical azimuth thrusters at the forward and aft of the vessel is chosen to accommodate these new demands.

Figure 1. (Left) W2W fleet size up to 2023. (Right) Order forecast of Wind farm support vessels up to 2030. Source – Clarkson’s Research, March 2024

This paper outlines the benefits of such a novel CSOV ship design, over a conventional offshore support vessel design. Firstly, the motivations for this paradigm change are studied, followed by a description of the new design. Then the performance of this new vessel design is compared with other similar vessels both qualitatively and quantitatively from several aspects.

2 C/SOV Vessel Design Philosophy

2.1 Description of the operational profile

The function and operational profile of C/SOVs are quite different from traditional offshore support vessels. CSOVs are primarily intended to perform a significant number of personnel & cargo transfer operations on each working day. These operations are to be performed as effortlessly as possible, so that specialized technicians can spend their working days as efficiently as possible. Depending on the type of operation, either construction or service, a typical day involves covering several Wind Turbine Generators (WTGs). At each wind farm site, the vessel transits at sailing speeds towards a WTG, after which Dynamic Positioning (DP) systems takeover to maneuver slowly but efficiently to reach the desired approach orientation and connect with the WTG landing platform via the vessel’s motion compensated access system. Personnel and cargo are then transferred via the access and crane system, after which the vessel maneuvers away and the process is repeated at other WTGs throughout the day. A typical operational profile of the C/SOV-type vessel can be summarized as below.

Table 1. Typical Annual Operational Profile of C/SOV vessels

Operation	% of Time spent Annually
Port time, bunkering, crew change	2%
Transit at economical speed	16%
Operation under DP2	50%
Standby under DP1	32%

Overall, these vessels spend around 80% of their annual operational time in low-speed maneuvering and in DP operations. Transit between WTGs within a wind farm is typically done at moderate speeds (up to 8 knots), since higher transit speeds are unsafe. Hence, it is important to have a vessel design which is optimized for this combination of operations.

2.2 Overview of the Traditional design and its Pitfalls

Considering these operational criteria, a CSOV design from a traditional approach would result in a vessel focused on maximum sailing speed and maximum DP capability. This would perfectly satisfy all required criteria but would be less efficient and less practical. Some of these limitations are summarized as follows:

- A hull shape optimized purely to reduce drag while sailing ahead has significant resistance while sailing astern even at slower speeds.
- With traditional offshore vessel thruster layouts, the aft thrusters are primarily installed for free-sailing and are typically under-utilized during maneuvering and DP, while the transverse/retractable thrusters in the bow are usually the limiting units. This limits the maneuvering and DP capability of the vessel.
- Tunnel thrusters are often used in the bow and are inefficient when compared with azimuth thrusters in terms of power consumption and response times.
- Tunnel thrusters generate more air-borne and structure-borne noise which increases noise and vibration levels onboard, impacting overall comfort. Significant investment in countermeasures and equipment is required to minimize this impact, and often not sufficient to provide the necessary comfort class notation.
- While retractable azimuth thrusters in the bow are more effective in low-speed maneuvering and DP operations, they increase integration complexity, cost, and maintenance.

These technical and practical considerations warranted a fundamental change to C/SOV design and topology.

2.3 Characteristics of New CSOV Design

After several design iterations and detailed discussions with vessel owners, operators and other stakeholders, a new concept was devised with a new hull and thruster layout as described in the following sections.

2.3.1 Thruster Layout

The most fundamental element of an offshore support vessel is the thruster layout, as this usually drives several other elements of vessel design. For the CSOV, the efficiency of personnel transfer operations can be significantly improved if the vessel's low-speed maneuvering capability can be increased. This requires a versatile and robust thruster layout along with quicker response times, while ensuring adequate redundancy for safety-critical transfer operations undertaken during DP.

For this purpose, Damen devised the DPX-DRIVE™ which features 4 identical fixed azimuth thrusters, symmetrically placed at each corner of the vessel, as outlined in **Figure 2** below.

Figure 2. Damen DPX™ Drive with 4 identical thrusters installed on the CSOV9020. ©Damen Shipyards Group

This has the following benefit in maneuvering & DP:

- Azimuth thrusters ensure quick response times in both propeller speed and steering speed enabling quicker omnidirectional movement & thrust vectoring.
- Identical thrusters ensure that at least 2 thrusters are online at both ends of the hull during a Worst-Case Single Failure (WCSF) providing a safe and reliable platform for transfer operations.
- The symmetric thruster layout with quick-response azimuth thrusters ensures a smaller DP footprint (accuracy of position-keeping) for the vessel thereby increasing its operability.

2.3.2 Hull Form

A significant benefit can be achieved if the vessel can maneuver equally well while sailing both ahead and astern. This can allow the vessel to approach WTGs in the most efficient orientation, with minimum number of maneuvers. Hence, in combination with the 4-thruster layout, this led to the design of a double-acting hull which retains high efficiency while sailing ahead at service speeds while providing significant resistance reduction while sailing astern at slow speeds up to 8 knots.

The hull consists of a sloped transom as opposed to a full and flat one, to minimize hydrodynamic pressure and encourage smoother flow while sailing astern. This is achieved without compromising on the valuable deck area. In the bow, the keel is raised to fit the thrusters, which can present a potential slamming issue, like the stern. However, at both ends, deep V-sections are made to reduce the amount of flat bottom area exposed to waves and hence minimize slamming impacts. The result is a double-ended ferry-like hull which has seemingly symmetric forward and aft ends.

Figure 3. Hull shape of the new CSOV Design showing the forward and aft ends of the vessel. ©Damen Shipyards Group

The resulting hull form design provides the following benefits to the CSOV platform:

- Minimized hydrodynamic drag while sailing astern at slow speeds while maintaining efficiency while sailing ahead.
- A symmetric submerged fore-aft hull shape when exposed to quartering waves exhibits a more symmetric wave and current moment behavior which is easier to offset by the thrusters. This in combination with the symmetric thruster layout, enables easier maneuvering in the wind parks, and allows the DP system to be optimized for efficiency apart from positional accuracy.

2.3.3 Additional Design Considerations

The identical and symmetric 4-thruster layout impacts other design considerations which are summarized below:

- Identical thrusters imply that all auxiliary equipment such as electric motors, drive systems, are also identical simplifying onboard electrical and control system architecture. This helps with easier troubleshooting, maintenance, spare parts availability etc.
- A simpler electrical and mechanical system layout enables a relatively easier system integration and commissioning of the various onboard systems, and an easier tuning of the DP control system.

3 Performance Assessment of The New CSOV Design

Throughout the design process, the new concept was developed through rigorous performance assessments, both semi-empirical and numerical, and eventually tested at model scale at the Maritime Research Institute of the Netherlands (MARIN). This chapter outlines the most relevant performance aspects of the new concept and offers both a quantitative and qualitative comparison with traditional vessels.

3.1 Dynamic Positioning

As discussed earlier, the DP capability for a CSOV vessel is especially important in determining the operability window of the vessel. In combination with its seakeeping aspects, DP capability enables safe transfer of personnel. This capability of the new CSOV vessel has been presented and compared with a traditional design.

3.1.1 Static DP Capability

Firstly, a comparison of static DP capability is performed which is a static balance of the environmental forces with the thruster forces. A simple thrust allocation algorithm is used to calculate the balancing thrust required for each heading, along with the power consumed based on the propeller characteristics.

To evaluate the performance of the ship in DP condition, a comparison with the Damen CSOV8720 has been performed. This comparison is performed for the actual propulsion layout of the new concept (4-thruster configuration) but also for the same hull form with a “traditional” propulsion layout taken from a previous generation SOV, which consists of 2 main stern thrusters, 2 retractable bow thrusters and one tunnel bow thruster. The hull is assumed to be the same for the purpose of this study, so the difference is ascribed only to the differences in propulsion. Hence the same wind coefficients and hydrodynamics coefficients (for waves and current) are used, along with identical wind and current areas. This is visualized in **Figure 4**. **Table 2** summarizes the propulsion arrangement used for the comparison.

Figure 4. Schematic comparing the outline of the 2 propulsion layouts. (*Left*) CSOV outline with the 4-thruster layout (*Right*) CSOV outline with traditional propulsion layout. Thruster sizes and positions are not to scale and shown for illustrative purposes only.

Table 2. Propulsion layouts for static DP Comparison

	Nominal Power [kW]	Propeller Diameter [m]	Nominal Thrust [kN]
CSOV - 4 thruster layout 4 x Main Azimuth Thrusters (2 x Forward + 2 x Aft)	1780	2.5	309
CSOV - Traditional Layout 2 x Main Azimuth Thrusters (Aft)	2150	2.8	351
2 x Retractable Forward Thrusters	600	1.6	99
1 x Tunnel Forward Thrusters	600	1.65	95

The comparison is made using MARIN’s software TRUST which has been developed within the Thrust Hydrodynamics JIP. The program is based on components from the Extensible Modelling Framework (XMF) library [1], which contains calculation models that are also used in many other MARIN software applications. In TRUST [4], the mean wind, wave, and current loads are calculated, after which the thrust required to counteract the environmental forces is determined. The performance is assessed for two environmental conditions (EC) as shown in the table below.

Table 3. Environmental condition for static DP assessment

EC	Waves		Wind speed	Current speed
	Hs [m]	Tp [s]	Vw [m/s]	Vc [m/s]
Medium	1.3	6.5	7.9	0.75
Heavy	3.1	8.5	13.8	0.75

Figure 5 below shows the required total power to keep the vessel in position for the above environmental conditions. The 4-thruster configuration needs an average (over all the headings) of approx. 35% less total power compared with the traditional layout configuration.

Figure 5 – Comparison of Required total thruster power during DP – (Left) Medium EC and (Right) heavy EC.

Figure 6. Required power at DP (Heavy EC) per individual thruster. (Left) Traditional layout. (Right) 4-Thruster layout

It should be highlighted that the total effective thrust (per heading) required is the same in both layouts, which is expected since the hulls and environmental conditions are the same. The difference in power therefore arises from the efficiency of the respective thrusters as explained below:

- Tunnel thrusters show a relatively high thrust degradation in current or in forward speed; in **Figure 6** the required power of both propulsion configurations is compared. The 4-thruster configuration has a symmetrical power distribution between the fore/aft thrusters and SB/PS. Whereas in the case of the traditional layout, the forward retractable thrusters and the tunnel bow thruster require higher power to provide the same thrust.
- In general, smaller propeller diameters are less efficient (Less thrust to power ratio) than larger ones. Tunnel thrusters also incur additional friction losses due to flow through the tunnel.
- Tunnel thrusters are also directionally limited compared to azimuth thrusters whose thrust vectors can be

varied omnidirectionally. This limitation is compensated by the main or retractable azimuth thrusters leading to higher usage of the thrusters overall.

- The propellers of the 4-thruster layout have been designed for DP (with maximum thrust available at 0 knots ship speed), and hence have a lower P/D. This is an advantage during DP but less efficient during free sailing. Traditional offshore vessels have main propellers designed for Free-sailing (Maximum thrust available at design speed) and hence are less efficient at 0 knots or in DP condition.

In Summary, considering a static DP assessment, it can be observed that the new CSOV design with the 4-thruster layout can keep position more efficiently with less power & fuel consumption.

3.1.2 Dynamic DP Capability

In contrast to static DP capability where forces are balanced statically, the dynamic DP capability takes the dynamics of all the sub-systems into account, including the vessel hydrodynamic response, thruster dynamics and DP control reactions. This provides a much more realistic behavior of the vessel during DP operations. In such studies, the primary output of interest is the footprint of the vessel, or the path traced by the vessel. The performance is then assessed by how well or often this footprint stays within a given target boundary (e.g., < 2m, <4m). This is called as DP accuracy or precision.

For this comparison, a time-domain dynamic positioning study performed by Damen for a similar vessel is used (70m version). The study compares the vessel footprint while in DP and the power consumption between a conventional thruster layout (CL) and the 4-thruster layout with double-ended hull (DE). It should be noted that the CL layout in this study utilizes 2 tunnel and 1 retractable, which is different from the conventional layout used in static DP comparison where 2 retractable and 1 tunnel thruster is used. The calculations were performed with MARIN's aNySIM Simulator platform [5], which is used for analysis of multibody dynamics in offshore operations. The two layouts for the comparison are shown below.

Figure 7. Comparison of the 2 layouts. (Left) conventional thruster layout (CL). (Right) 4-thruster layout (DE)

The DP control system in the model consists of a Proportional–integral–derivative (PID) controller which uses the error between the required vessel position and the measured vessel position (surge, sway, and yaw) to derive the required force/moments. An allocation algorithm calculates the thrust (magnitude and direction) to be assigned to the different thrusters. The thrust allocated to each propulsion device is such that the sum of thrust magnitudes and the sum of moments applied to the ship equals those required by the PID controller to counteract the environmental loads. The resulting allocation minimizes the required power by the propulsion devices and considers thrust magnitude and direction limitations.

As the input for the PID controller is based on the vessel motions (due to environmental influences), and the same hull form/loading condition is used for both configurations, the same control gain settings are considered applicable for both configurations. It should be noted that this study was not focused on optimizing the control system for DP performance, but rather on comparing the DP performance of the two propulsion configurations.

Using aNySIM, several fast-time simulations are performed subjecting the vessel to environmental conditions (shown in **Table 4**) consisting of irregular waves, wind, and current approaching from different headings for a time span of 3 hours. From the resulting time trace, a mean offset or the deviation from its target or reference position is plotted for each heading. Additionally, an indication is given on the average power consumption of the vessel during the simulation.

Table 4. Summary of environmental conditions for Dynamic DP Capability assessment

Condition	Waves Hs [m]	Wind Vw [m/s]	Current Vc [m/s]
Medium	2.0	12.0	0.50
Heavy	2.5	14.0	0.75

The following figures present the response and behavior of the combined vessel & DP system to the above environmental conditions.

Figure 8. Medium condition - Polar plot comparison of conventional thruster layout and 4-thruster layout: (Left) Mean offset from target position in meters. (Right) Mean power usage in kW.

Figure 9. Heavy condition - Polar plot comparison of conventional thruster layout and 4-thruster layout. (Left) Mean offset from target position in meters. (Right) Mean power usage in kW.

The mean offsets in the medium conditions of both configurations are remarkably similar. In the heavy condition, the mean offset is also similar except in beam seas where CL has higher offsets as limits of the bow tunnel thrusters are reached often. The dynamic offsets and footprint were found to be similar (not presented here).

Comparing the average power consumption, the 4-thruster layout overall is found to consume up to 19% less power in both environmental conditions, with highest reductions found in bow quartering and beam seas. This is also where the efficiency of the forward azimuth thrusters of the DE configuration is found to be better than that of the tunnel thrusters of the CL configuration.

In summary, the 2 configurations provide similar performances up to medium environmental conditions. However, as conditions get more severe, the conventional layout starts to reach some of its thruster limits whereas the 4-thruster layout can operate more efficiently. The average power consumption is clearly found to be lower in the 4-thruster layout in both environmental conditions.

Overall, the 4-thruster layout is found to provide significantly lower power & fuel consumption and marginally better Dynamic DP performance (DP accuracy)

3.2 Calm Water Resistance & Powering

To assess the design's free-sailing efficiency, it is important to understand the resistance and propulsion characteristics to a high degree of accuracy. Hence a systematic Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) campaign was performed both for the hull and its appendages followed by an extensive towing tank test campaign.

3.2.1 CFD Hull Optimizations

The calm-water resistance performance of the new hull shape and all its appendages were analyzed numerically using Damen's in-house CFD capabilities before model testing at MARIN. The focus during CFD was to minimize drag while sailing ahead up to 14 knots and while sailing astern up to 8 knots.

For efficient sailing both ahead and astern, several improvements were made. The volume distribution across the length of the vessel was made as symmetric as possible, while slightly favoring sailing ahead at design speed. This makes a better compromise in the wave-making resistance in both sailing directions. The transom was sloped as much as possible to avoid creating a stagnation point while sailing astern.

In **Figure 10**, the hydrodynamic pressure coefficient (C_p) obtained from CFD is compared at the same speed of 12.5 knots to enable a fair comparison. As intended, the stagnation pressure at the transom is reduced while sailing astern, owing to the sloped and pointed transom design. This creates a smoother wave pattern along the hull compared to the sailing ahead condition.

Figure 10. Hydrodynamic Pressure (Coefficient of pressure) and wave pattern along the hull while sailing at 12.5knots as obtained from CFD simulations. (*Top*) Sailing Ahead, (*Bottom*) Sailing Astern

The resistance coefficients while sailing ahead and astern are compared along with the pressure and frictional components in **Figure 11**. As expected, the astern condition has slightly higher resistance mainly from the pressure component, as the transom has a larger entrance angle compared to the bow. But overall, the difference in total resistance is ~6% at 8 knots which is deemed reasonable considering the shape.

Figure 11. Comparison of CFD resistance coefficients while sailing ahead and astern

3.2.2 Resistance & Powering Model Tests

After the CFD hull-form optimization, MARIN built a suitable ship model including all appendages and performed resistance tests in the Deep-Water Towing tank (DT). The goal was to determine the ship's resistance and validate the results of the CFD calculations. The resistance test, in combination with the self-propulsion tests, allows to determine the ship's propulsion coefficients, such as thrust deduction, wake fraction and propulsive efficiency. This information is particularly interesting in this project to make a suitable comparison with other designs.

Prior to the self-propulsion model test, MARIN also performed an optimization test to determine the optimal power distribution between the forward and aft thrusters. This is to determine what % of the total propulsion power should be distributed to the forward and aft thrusters to minimize power consumption. This can be different for different speeds as wake from the forward thrusters interacting with the inflow to the aft thrusters are different at different speeds.

Figure 12 - Self-propulsion model tests for the Damen CSOV as performed at MARIN's towing tank (pictured while sailing at 14kn)

This power distribution optimization test was performed at both 8 and 12.5kn. As can be seen in **Figure 13** below, the optimal distribution depends on the speed. The optimal power distribution at 8kn speed would be approx. 85/15 (aft/fore). This means that 85% of the propulsion power required to sail at 8 knots is delivered by the 2 aft thrusters, and 15% by the 2 forward thrusters. Since the design speed of the vessel is 12.5kn, a power distribution of 80/20 (aft/fore) was selected and used further in the self-propulsion tests. This prioritizes the design speed, while offering a good balance at the transit speed of 8 kn. In practice the ship operator should take this into account during the operation of the ship to optimize the fuel consumption.

Figure 13 - Results of power distribution optimization test taken from Model Tests for 8 and 12.5kn.

Figure 14 below shows the net force of the forward thruster units (F_x) measured at the connection point of the thruster unit with the hull. The optimal power distribution is achieved when this F_x force is zero or when the forward thrusters are generating enough thrust to overcome their own resistance when sailing at a certain speed.

Figure 14 - Unit force (F_x) measured during the model tests – The results suggest that when the Forward thrusters provide ~22% of the total power, their resistance is zero.

From the figure above, we observe that approx. 20% of this power is used to overcome the resistance of the forward thrusters, and this reduces the propulsive efficiency (η_D) of the vessel.

The propulsive efficiency for a ship is defined as follows:

$$\eta_D = \frac{P_E}{P_D} = \eta_H \times \eta_0 \times \eta_R ; \text{ where } \eta_H = \frac{1 - t}{1 - w} \quad (1)$$

Considering that without the presence of the forward thrusters, only 80% of the power would be required to propel the vessel at the same speed, the η_D would then have been 0.501 which is very comparable to similar vessels as will be shown later in 3.2.4.

3.2.3 Resistance Comparison - CFD and Model Tests

One of the objectives of the MARIN model tests was to allow for the verification of the CFD resistance calculations performed by DAMEN.

Table 5 - Comparison of Resistance coefficients between CFD & Model tests for the Damen CSOV

Speed [knots]	Fn [-]	CT_CFD [-]	CA [-]	CT + Ca [-]	Comparison between CFD & Model tests [%]
6.0	0.11	2.49E-03	6.5E-04	3.14E-03	-6%
8.0	0.14	2.57E-03	6.5E-04	3.22E-03	-4%
9.5	0.17	2.73E-03	6.5E-04	3.38E-03	-2%
11.0	0.19	3.07E-03	6.5E-04	3.72E-03	1%
12.5	0.22	3.54E-03	6.5E-04	4.19E-03	3%

Table 5 shows this comparison, the difference varies between -6% to +3%. In this comparison, it was essential to add a correlation allowance (CA) to the CFD results, and the same CA as determined for the model tests. The CA_{Basic} is determined using the Grigson friction line with the following formula, given by the MARIN 3D method:

$$CA_{Basic} = 0.0058(L + 100)^{-0.16} - 0.00196 \quad (2)$$

The CA_{Basic} would be equal to 0.000552. However, based on statistical data of MARIN, a value of 0.00065 was used. If this CA is not added to the CFD results, the difference would have been larger (~34% at 6 kn to 15% at 12.5kn).

3.2.4 Performance comparison with Similar Ships

To get a better understanding of its resistance & propulsion performance, the new Damen CSOV is compared with similar offshore support vessels with traditional thruster arrangement (2 main thrusters in the aft and one or two bow thruster(s) in the fore ship). The comparison is performed using the admiralty coefficient (AC). The comparison is presented in two stages.

First to judge the quality of the hull, AC_{RES} is used which allows non-dimensional comparison using only hull parameters and its flow regime.

$$AC_{Res} = \frac{0.7477 \times V_S^3 \times \nabla^{2/3}}{P_E} \quad (3)$$

Where P_E is the effective power required by the hull with a displacement of ∇ , with resistance R_T when towed at speed V_S .

And secondly, to evaluate the propulsive performance, AC_{PROP} is used which allows non-dimensional comparison including the effect of the thrusters.

$$AC_{Prop} = \frac{0.7477 \times V_S^3 \times \nabla^{2/3}}{P_D} \quad (3)$$

Where P_D is the delivered power by the thruster propellers, required to self-propel the ship.

Three additional vessels have been selected for this comparison. PSV-type and ROV-type vessels are added here as they are traditional offshore support vessels which are usually also retrofitted for W2W operations, and an additional ship from MARIN database (state-of-the-art SOV vessel) has been also included as reference. Their dimensional parameters are presented in **Table 6** below.

Table 6 - Main particulars of reference ships used in the comparative study.

Particulars	Symbol	MARIN DB	CSOV8720	PSV	ROV	Unit
LCB position (from midship)	LCB	+1.60	-1.20	+2.20	+0.85	%
Block coefficient	C_B	0.736	0.629	0.681	0.628	-
Midship (ordinate 10) coeff.	C_M	0.993	0.982	0.987	0.947	-
Prismatic coefficient	C_P	0.738	0.641	0.69	0.663	-
Length-Breadth ratio	L_{pp}/B	3.983	4.452	4.648	4.222	-
Breadth-Draught ratio	B/T	3.60	4.062	3.60	3.273	-

All the ships except the Damen CSOV8720 present a classical propulsion approach for SOV's with 2 main thrusters and two bow thrusters as shown in **Table 7**.

Table 7 - Propulsion Arrangement of Reference Ships used in comparative study.

	Bow thrusters	Main thrusters	Nozzle Type
MARIN DB	2	2	HR
CSOV8720	0	2+2	19A
PSV75	2	2	19A
ROV83	2	2	19B

The data of the reference ships has been corrected for (small) differences in main dimensions, form coefficients etc., by means of the methodology of DESP (based on Holtrop&Mennen method [6] and valid for displacement ships up to $F_n = 0.8$). This way the differences between test results only depend on the quality of the hull form and not anymore on the main dimensions and fullness. The hull form that has the highest level of AC_{Res} is the best.

Figure 15 - Comparison of Hull Quality with similar ships (higher value indicates better hull quality) - The actual values have been normalized by the AC_{RES} of the MARIN DB reference ship.

In **Figure 15**, the two SOV-type hulls are seen to perform the best compared to the other two in terms of hull quality (hull resistance). It is worth pointing out that PSV and ROV vessels are generally designed to carry cargo and have different design constraints than CSOVs which are designed to carry personnel mainly. So, it is not unexpected that they are less efficient than SOVs.

Comparing within the SOV type hulls, the performance between both the MARIN DB ship and the CSOV8720 is similar up to 9kn, after which the MARIN DB shows about 10% higher performance. This is found to be reasonable since a compromised hull form was selected for the CSOV to improve astern sailing and to fit the forward thrusters. It also shows that the hull design of the CSOV is more efficient compared to hulls with “traditional” propulsion arrangement, such as the PSV-type and ROV-type.

In conclusion, although the new CSOV hull form was designed as a compromise to achieve better maneuvering & DP performance, the resistance is found to be the same, if not better compared to benchmark hull forms which are of more traditional design.

The same comparison can be performed to show the effect of the propulsion arrangement, using AC_{PROP} , which uses delivered power P_D instead of the effective power.

Figure 16 - Comparison of hull and propulsion efficiency with similar ships (higher value indicates better hull quality and propulsion performance) - The actual values have been normalized by the AC_{PROP} of the MARIN DB reference ship

Based on **Figure 16**, the AC_{PROP} of the CSOV8720 is 20% lower than that of the MARIN reference ship. This is due to the difference in thruster configurations. This reduction in efficiency points out to the additional drag due to the presence of the 2 forward azimuth thrusters as discussed in 3.2.2.

Ultimately, it is also revealing to compare the relation between AC_{RES} and AC_{PROP} , or in other words, the relation between P_E and P_D , and this is represented by the propulsive efficiency η_D (1).

Figure 17 - Comparison of Propulsive Efficiency (η_D) of the different reference ships used in comparison.

Overall, the following conclusions can be made regarding the resistance and powering performance of the Damen CSOV vessel with regards to similar vessels:

- When comparing resistance performance in the form of AC_{RES} , the new CSOV is one of the best ships.
- However, when comparing the powering performance in the form of AC_{PROP} , clearly shows the penalty that the new CSOV8720 must pay due to the additional 2 fixed forward thrusters, especially when compared to the MARIN DB or the ROV-type.
- The propulsive performance η_D of the Damen CSOV is found to be the lowest, again due to the penalty of the fixed forward thrusters. However, knowing that these thrusters represent a penalty of about 20%, a hypothetical ship with a hull form similar to the CSOV would achieve η_D values similar to the MARIN DB vessel or other traditional vessel.

Although this minor drawback of the forward azimuth thrusters during transit operations was anticipated, its operational impact is minimal compared to their critical role in dynamic positioning operations which accounts for

nearly 80% of the vessel’s operational profile (See 2.1). Alternatives such as retractable thrusters would reduce the symmetric hydrodynamics of the 4-thruster layout, increase structural integration complexity, and add to costs, while bringing very modest gains during the limited transit times.

3.2.5 Full-scale Powering Tests

The first vessel of this new CSOV series underwent rigorous sea acceptance tests where the unique combination of the 4-thruster layout was also tested. Specifically, the power distribution between the forward and aft thrusters during transit operation was varied as was done during the model tests, to determine the optimal power split.

These speed-power trials were performed and analyzed by Damen in consultation with MARIN, and in accordance with [1]. 4 different power distributions (Aft/Fwd) were tested – 100/0, 90/10, 80/20 and 65/35. Instead of testing the distributions at a fixed target speed, these were executed at a target total propulsion power. This is because maintaining a fixed vessel speed-over-ground (SOG) over two complete runs with a full-scale ship is practically not feasible.

For each distribution, one forward and one return runs are executed. The tests are started with the 100/0 configuration where all the target propulsion power is delivered by the two aft thrusters, and the two forward thrusters are left in a windmilling condition. The return power from the windmilling thrusters is not fed back into the energy grid and as such is not considered in the power analysis. For the other distributions, the thruster speeds are adjusted during the forward runs such that the target power is distributed as required before logging the runs, and the lever settings are unchanged for the return runs.

Table 8 – Summary of full-scale power distribution speed measurements

Speed Run Leg	1a	1b	2a	2b	3a	3b	4a	4b
Target Power Split (Aft/Fwd)	100 / 0	100 / 0	90 / 10	90 / 10	80 / 20	80 / 20	65 / 35	65 / 35
Measured Power split	100 / 0	100 / 0	89 / 11	90 / 10	80 / 20	79 / 21	65 / 35	65 / 35
Closeness to Target propulsion Power	0.98	0.97	0.95	0.96	0.95	0.88	0.96	0.91

The measured speed and powers are corrected for ideal trial conditions in accordance with [2]. An average speed of ~11kn across the 4 distributions is determined, and the total propulsion power required in each of the distribution to achieve this speed is calculated from the tests and compared with model-scale results in Figure 18.

Figure 18 – Comparison of propulsion power in different distributions in full-scale (2400kW) and model-scale (12.5knots), presented as a reduction in power required, normalized with power required for 100/0 configuration. For simplicity, the model-scale 75/25 result and the full-scale 80/20 result are plotted on the same vertical line.

In general, it can be seen that the full-scale vessel is significantly more efficient when the forward thrusters are driven, with a minimum efficiency gain of 3.6% compared to when thrusters are not powered and left windmilling. The most efficient configuration is found to be the 80/20 power split which is almost 6% more efficient than 100/0, and 2% more efficient than the other two tested configurations. This aligns well with the conclusions drawn from the power distribution tests performed during model tests described in 3.2.2 where the optimum power split was found to be around 85/15 for 8 knots and 75/25 at 12.5 knots.

3.3 Seakeeping

As mentioned in 3.1, operability and comfort are paramount for the CSOV vessels. A big driving force for operability is how the ship responds to 1st order waves (dominant wave periods) and if they can stay within the mechanical limits of the motion-compensation access systems. The lower the response, the higher the operability, and safer for transfer of personnel. Similarly, lower ship responses lead to lower slamming, lower accelerations onboard and better and comfortable experience overall for crew and personnel.

With a new hull and thruster concept, it was important to assess the seakeeping performance of the vessel through model tests. This was done at MARIN's Seakeeping and Maneuvering Basin (SMB). The same model was used as for the resistance & powering tests. The model was self-propelled for tests at speed and fixed with soft springs for tests at zero speed. The model was equipped with four identical azimuth thrusters, a network of sensors and a standalone signal acquisition system. It was only connected to the carriage via power and data cables, arranged to avoid affecting its free-body motion. The vessel's U-type anti-roll tank (ART) was also optimized and installed within the ship's model to include its effects on seakeeping. The respective models are shown in **Figure 19**.

Figure 19 - Seakeeping model as tested at MARIN's SMB, along with the U-type ART.

The tests were focused on the seakeeping behavior of the vessel in irregular wave conditions at zero speed, which is the most critical condition for transfer operations at sea. Three different sea states were tested in several vessel headings as outlined in the table below. Additionally, roll resonance tests were performed to assess the roll damping behavior of the vessel and the ART.

Table 9 – Irregular Sea states tested for seakeeping behavior in MARIN's SMB

Sea state	Wave period (Tp) [s]	Significant wave height (Hs) [m]	Wave Headings [Degrees]
A	8.4	2.1	0, 45, 90, 135, 180
B	9.0	2.5	0, 45, 90, 135, 180
C	8.5	3.1	0, 45, 90, 135, 180

The following observations and conclusions are made from the seakeeping tests at zero speed.

- The ART was found to provide a roll-reduction of ~40% at the roll resonance period for waves heights of 4m. The ART thus significantly helps reduce the roll motions and hence improves comfort and

- operability of the vessel even in the severest of conditions.
- The vessel exhibits distinct fore-aft symmetric behavior in roll, pitch, and heave motions because of the hull shape that was designed to improve astern performance.
- Roll and Pitch root mean square (RMS) values stayed below 1.5 degrees for all sea states and headings. The max roll RMS was calculated at 1.1 degrees for beam-seas.
- The most critical limit of the gangway system is the telescoping compensation speed limit. For most gangway equipment, the technical limit is ~2.5m/s but 2.0m/s is used for this study also considering human factors. From the tests, the vessel movement at the gangway tip was found to not exceed this value up to sea state B, and exceed less than 1% of the time for sea state C. This shows good confidence in the vessel design to provide a reliable transfer platform with high operability even in severe seas.
- The measured accelerations at the bridge, mess and forward most cabins remained within acceptable comfort levels, according to the personnel criteria limits established under NATO STANAG 4154 guidelines.
- Green water events on any part of the deck were not observed for any test condition.
- Slamming was observed in the bow, particularly in head sea and bow-quartering seas in sea state B and C. This is a result of the raised bow shape compared to traditional vessels and is one of the disadvantages of the design. However, additional strength and fatigue assessments were performed to ensure slamming pressures do not damage the structure or disrupt gangway operations.

3.4 Comfort

Since CSOV vessels carry specialized crew and technicians who are mostly land-based and have limited acclimatization with sailing in moderate seas, comfort is particularly important, as reduction in the effectiveness of the personnel lowers the operability of the complete vessel operation.

Traditional offshore support vessels, particularly outfitted for DP operations, invariably consist of one or more bow and stern tunnel thrusters (including retractable thrusters). In these types of vessels, maneuvering and DP operations involve significant use of tunnel thrusters which generate large amount of both air-borne and structure-borne noise [7]. The main source of both air-borne and structure-borne noise is the cavitation at the propeller blades which is then permeated into the ship structure via the propeller blades as well as the tunnel walls, and the machinery itself.

While air-borne noise is more easily attenuated before it reaches the accommodation space, structure-borne noise is notoriously more difficult. Hence the bow thruster noise can often be heard up to several decks, especially in the forward area even with additional acoustic countermeasures. In offshore support vessels, most accommodation spaces are located between the midship and the bow of the ship as the aft space is usually reserved for machinery, workshops, and storage. Hence comfort in these vessels during DP and maneuvering operations is relatively lower. Air injection system in newer vessels helps reduce the amount of air bubbles being generated during the thruster operation but the remaining noise can still be disruptive in several cabin spaces. For a vessel which stays in DP conditions for 80% of the time, comfort is therefore particularly important.

In the new CSOV design with DPX Drive™, the tunnel and retractable thrusters are replaced with 2 L-drive azimuth thrusters. Hence the only reduction gearing is inside the thruster hub, and the whole unit is situated outside the hull which reduces the permeation of vibrations from the gearing into the rest of the hull. Unlike with tunnel thrusters, noise from cavitation is significantly minimized as the air bubbles do not interact and implode on the tunnel walls within the ship construction. Although cavitation does occur with azimuth thrusters, their implosion is not effectively carried through to the ship structure because the cavitation source is further away, generating less noise. Overall, some structure-borne noise from the azimuth thruster operation is transferred to the hull, however the levels are significantly reduced.

To get a quantitative understanding of the differences between the 2 arrangements, full scale measurements made onboard a vessel which has both type of thrusters can be utilized. For this purpose, a similar Damen vessel with a traditional propulsion layout of 2 tunnel thrusters and retractable thrusters in the bow, and 2 main azimuth thrusters in the aft is chosen. The schematic of the layout is illustrated in **Figure 20** and its configuration is listed in **Table 10**.

Figure 20 – Propulsion arrangement of reference Damen vessel and locations of sound measurements while in DP operations. 1 – Bow thruster room, 2 – Main thruster room

Table 10 – Comparison of Sound Pressure levels in propulsion rooms between Forward and Aft

	Forward Propulsion Room (1)	Aft Propulsion Room (2)
Configuration	2 x tunnel thrusters 1 x retractable azimuth thruster	2 x Z-drive Azimuth Thruster
Nominal Power (Complete room)	2580 kW	4300 kW
Power During DP (40% of Nominal)	1032 kW	1720kW
Average Sound Pressure Level	96 dB(A)	86 dB(A)

Noise measurements using calibrated devices and approved personnel were conducted during DP condition where all thrusters are running at 40% of nominal power as required by class notation. Several measurements were conducted at different points in both propulsion rooms. The average sound pressure level was then calculated.

As seen in **Table 10**, the aft propulsion room with 2 fixed azimuth thrusters is almost 10 dB(A) quieter than the forward propulsion room with traditional tunnel and retractable thrusters, even with the aft propulsion room having almost double the propulsion power. Although minor differences exist in the type and size of the propulsion space between the forward and aft areas, this gives a good indication of the difference in the noise levels generated between the two types of propulsion. The noise generated in the propulsion rooms propagates to the rest of the ship and to the accommodation space.

Hence with the new Damen CSOV platform, replacing the forward tunnel thrusters with fixed azimuth thrusters, especially with L-drive azimuth thrusters, the noise and vibration levels at the source is expected to be significantly lower. Consequently, the inherent noise and vibration levels in the ship are reduced, and expensive acoustic countermeasures can be minimized. This helps improve the overall comfort onboard.

3.5 Costs

Costs are also a big consideration for SOV operators and the competition in the offshore wind market drives operators to lower costs further. For the comparison between the new CSOV and traditional SOVs, the costs are split into two as described in the following sections.

3.5.1 CAPEX

In comparing the CAPEX between the new and old CSOV designs, the analysis showed that the costs were equal or slightly lower. This analysis is based on indicative prices of ship components and not actual quotes from suppliers. Hence the actual price differences may vary. However, based on this indicative pricing analysis, it was seen that the CAPEX difference would not be significant.

3.5.2 OPEX

When comparing OPEX, the difference between the traditional and new design comes down to the fuel consumption during operation, which in turn relates to the total power consumption. As the CSOV vessels are

primarily operating in DP conditions (~80% annually), a comparison of the power consumption during DP operation is considered most significant for the overall OPEX of the vessel.

As was seen from section 3.1, Damen's 4 thruster DPX drive solution consumes less average power up to 19% and even up to 22% in lighter environmental conditions. This directly translates to lower fuel consumption assuming diesel-electric arrangement or similar.

3.6 Maintenance

During operations, normal wear and tear and occasional breakdown of components is expected. And breakdown or malfunction of critical components such as generators, propulsion motors, propulsion frequency drives, electrical switchboards etc. can lead to failures, and any operation is terminated till the problem component or issues are fixed. Breakdown of non-critical components may not cause termination of operation but would still need to be replaced.

For failures of both critical & non-critical components, the parts either must be fixed or replaced while underway or at port. And if spares are not readily available, this can keep the vessel out of operation, which can be expensive.

For traditional offshore support vessels, the thruster topology includes at least 2 or 3 different types of thrusters (Stern propulsion thruster, bow tunnel thruster, retractable bow thruster, etc.). Consequently, these different types of thrusters require different auxiliary machinery such as electric motors, frequency drives, distribution cables, etc. Consequently, to avoid significant impact on operations in case of failures, spares for the different types of components must be procured and kept available onboard or at a dedicated facility designated by the owner, increasing complexity of spare parts management and with an impact on the CAPEX and OPEX of the ship that depends on inventory and logistical procedures of the Shipowner.

For the new CSOV with DPX Drive, all 4 thrusters are identical, which means identical auxiliary machinery too. This enables us to have just 1 or 2 sets of spares per vessel (or per fleet) for the expensive critical components. This simplifies procuring and maintaining the spares for the critical components which can only be fixed at port. The same is true for components which can be maintained onboard. Overall, onboard maintenance and spare parts inventory is expected to be easier and less expensive for the operators.

4 Conclusions

A new CSOV vessel design was found to be necessary due to the increased demand from the offshore wind industry in terms of operability, comfort, and efficiency. To suit the required operational profile of such vessels which was mostly low-speed maneuvering and DP, Damen devised the DPX Drive™ with four identical non-retractable azimuth thrusters along with a double-acting hull. This new design is then compared with traditional designs with conventional propulsion layouts from several performance aspects.

From a DP perspective, the new CSOV is found to be notably better than its traditional counterparts. Both static and Dynamic Capability assessments show that the new CSOV requires significantly less power consumption (and hence less fuel consumption) to keep position in the same environmental conditions. The dynamic study also showed a slightly lower station-keeping footprint for the new CSOV.

The new CSOV is found to have similar if not better calm-water resistance performance while sailing ahead compared to traditionally designed offshore vessels. With a modified hull form, resistance while sailing astern was only slightly higher compared to sailing ahead. However, when including the propulsion aspects, the vessel is found to be less efficient primarily due to the presence of the two additional non-retractable forward thrusters. Overall, this is considered acceptable as free sailing is an exceedingly small part of the operational profile. Furthermore, to improve efficiency while sailing, optimum power distribution between forward and aft thrusters is implemented as obtained from model-scale and full-scale testing.

Replacing tunnel thrusters with azimuth thrusters also reduces onboard noise and improves comfort as was shown by measurements on similar vessels. In terms of the costs, the CAPEX is found to be similar, while OPEX is expected to be lower due to lowering in fuel consumptions during DP operations. While maintenance and spare parts inventory is expected to be easier due to identical auxiliary systems and a simpler electrical system layout. Finally, the simpler layout also enables easier commissioning, tuning, and troubleshooting of the systems both during the build-phase and operations.

Overall, this new design paradigm provides a more efficient, comfortable, reliable, and all-round improved CSOV vessel platform which ticks all the boxes of the increased demands set by an ever-growing offshore wind industry.

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